

THE CONUNDRUM OF THE INTERIM AWARD IN THE INDIAN ARBITRATION DOMINION: THE IMMINENT WAY AHEAD

by

Yash Patil

ABSTRACT

In Indian arbitration processes, the granting of Interim Awards is a technique that is less often used but is not a new idea. Its usage can be traced all the way back to the beginning of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, which was passed in 1996 itself. This apparently basic clause, on the other hand, is plagued with ambiguities that make it difficult for Indian courts to maintain the pro-arbitration attitude that is now prevalent in the country. This article reviews the judicial treatment of the provision up to this point in the context of pragmatic realities such as costs, the possibility of using the provision as a delay tactic, and the limited statutory prescription. Because the jurisprudence on the subject is limited, this article reviews the judicial treatment of the provision. In light of the recent observations made by the Supreme Court in the Bhadra Products case, in which the court recommended to Parliament that the challenge of the interim award be clubbed with the challenge of the final award under Section 34 to avoid 'piecemeal challenges' and reduce costs, it is important to note that this recommendation was made. When parties are denied access to such a remedy at the interim stage, it is required to conduct an analysis of the far-reaching effects that this decision will have. In addition, the article calls into question the substantial discretion that is vested in the tribunal and, later, the courts, which is the foundation upon which the implementation of the provision is based. The article also discusses tangential topics, such as whether or not it is legal to contract out of Section 31(6) of the Act and whether or not it is possible to get an interim award based on an admission of culpability. This article explores the need and extent to which the interim award provisions should be amended for a greater degree of certainty, uniformity, and compliance with international standards. Considering the lack of discussion on the aforementioned provision in the recommendations of the 246th Law Commission Report and the Arbitration & Conciliation (Amendment) Act 2018, this article investigates whether or not the interim award provisions should be amended.

INTRODUCTION

Section 2(1)(c)¹ of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996 (often referred to simply as ‘the Act’) specifies that a “arbitral award” must include a ‘interim award,’ which is also sometimes referred to as a “partial award.” As stated in subsection (6) of section 31 of the Act, which grants the Arbitral Tribunal this authority, the Arbitral Tribunal possesses the authority to issue an interim award on “any subject with regard to which the Tribunal may make a final arbitral judgement.”² This authority empowers the arbitral tribunal to make a ruling on everything the arbitral tribunal can make a final ruling. When the arbitral tribunal has not yet become *functus officio*, an award that is made during the interim stage³ of the dispute can have the characteristics of both a final award and an interim award. This is because it can definitively determine the rights and liabilities of the parties involved in the dispute on a particular issue and it can compel them to act in accordance with its findings.⁴ The second way that an interim award might take effect is if the form of the award is such that it is meant to have effect only so long as the final award is in effect. This is the case when the award is designed to have effect only so long as the final award is in effect.⁵ An argument may often be presented in one of two ways: It is a common method that is employed by tribunals, and it allows them to describe the problems (such as jurisdiction, responsibility, applicable legislation, etc.) that are in dispute and, where appropriate, to determine specific matters at an early stage of the proceedings.⁶ According to the findings of a research project that was carried out in 2012 by Queen Mary University in conjunction with White and Case LLP, partial or interim awards are handed down in about one third of all instances in international arbitration procedures.⁷ This conclusion demonstrates the importance of adhering to its principles within the framework of the domestic arbitration procedure. It is imperative to differentiate between an interim award that is issued in accordance with the Act and an interim or partial award that is issued in certain international and institutional arbitrations by an emergency arbitrator. An interim award is one that is issued in accordance with the Act when it is issued in accordance with the Act. An interim arbitral award may be challenged in accordance with Section 34 of the Act, which is a provision of the Act. This is because the description of what constitutes an ‘arbitral award’ includes the interim arbitral award as one of the elements that must be present. In addition, an arbitrator has the discretionary power to submit many interim awards at any particular point in time.⁸ As a result, the granting of interim awards in India is founded on two weak foundations: the uncertain components of an interim

¹ Arbitration & Conciliation Act 1996 § 2(1)(c).

² Arbitration & Conciliation Act 1996 § 31(6).

³ McDermott International Inc. v. Burn Standard Co. Ltd., (2006) 11 SCC 181, ¶68-70.

⁴ Satwant Singh Sodhi v. State of Punjab, (1999) 3 SCC 487, ¶6.

⁵ Satwant Singh Sodhi v. State of Punjab, (1999) 3 SCC 487, ¶6.

⁶ Harsh Hari Haran, Do Parties Need Recourse against Interim Awards?, WOLTERS KLUWER ARBITRATION,

<http://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2018/09/06/parties-need-recourse-interim-awards/>

⁷ Queen’s Mary, White & Case LLP, 2012 International Arbitration Survey: Current and Preferred Practices in the Arbitral Process, p. 38,

https://arbitration.qmul.ac.uk/media/arbitration/docs/2012_International_Arbitration_Survey.pdf

⁸ ONGC v. Anil Construction Co., AIR 2000 Guj 284.

award and the uneven judicial handling of the award itself. In other words, the awarding of interim awards in India is built on two wobbly pillars.

CONFIGURATION UNDER TAINTY: DETERMINES THE NATURE OF THE MID-PRICE.

Nevertheless, it does not define what constitutes an interim award nor does it offer clarity on the thin line that divides such an award from an interim measure in accordance with Section 9 and Section 17 of the Act. This is due to the fact that the Indian arbitration process, which is related to the Act, allows for the filing of an interim award, followed by the subsequent challenge of that judgement. Because a jurisdictional award and an interim measure can be challenged under Section 34⁹ and Section 37¹⁰ of the Act, respectively, it is necessary to determine the nature of the award while also accurately identifying the statutorily mandated recourse against it. This becomes necessary when it becomes clear that a jurisdictional award and an interim measure can be challenged. Having said that, this must be accomplished while concurrently determining the statutorily required course of action to take against it.

It would appear that the Honourable Supreme Court has indicated that one of the criteria for an order to take on the nature of an award or an interim award is that the decision must be of a dispute or claim arising out of, or relating to, the agreement.¹¹ This seems to be one of the criteria for an order to take on the nature of an award or an interim award. One of the requirements for an order to be given the status of an award or an interim award is that it must pass this test. It has been observed that it would not be conducive to interpret the decision of the Joint Arbitration Committee with regard to the venue as an interim award, which would confer a right of challenge to an aggrieved person under Section 34 of the Act.¹² This is because an interpretation of the decision as an interim award would make it more likely that the decision would be challenged. This is due to the fact that if the judgement were to be interpreted as an interim award, then the likelihood of the decision being challenged would increase. The arbitrator is obligated to render a ruling about a part of the dispute that has been presented to him; he may decide upon some of the issues or some of the claims that are connected to the dispute.¹³ This is accomplished via the use of a provisional award. When the tribunal just recorded the judgement that the majority of the business's shareholders did not wish a division of the assets possessed by the company, a statement of fact such as this did not constitute an interim award; rather, it was only a statement of the facts. Given the circumstances at the time, it was determined that it was not the appropriate time to

⁹ Wording of Section 34 provides that recourse against an 'arbitral award' may be made only by an application for setting aside the award in accordance with sub-section (2) and (3) of Section 34. Since, sub-section (c) of Section 2 provides that an arbitral award shall include an interim award, it is necessarily concluded that an interim award can also be challenged only under Section 34 of the Arbitration Act.

¹⁰ Clause (b) of sub-section (1) of Section 37 and clause (b) of sub-section (2) of Section 37 provide for appeal against orders granting or refusing to grant any interim measure under Section 9 and Section 17 of the Act respectively.

¹¹ *Sanshin Chemicals Industry v. Orientals Carbons & Chemicals Ltd.*, (2001) 3 SCC 341.

¹² *Id.*

¹³ 1 A. WADHWA & A. KRISHNAN, JUSTICE RS BACHAWAT'S LAW OF ARBITRATION 1684 (6 ed. Lexis Nexis 2018).

submit an application in accordance with Section 34 of the Act. This decision was reached as a result of the previous sentence.¹⁴

What are the key differences between a ‘judgement on jurisdiction’ and a ‘interim award’?

Another contentious issue that has been brought up in connection with this is the fact that there have been cases in which interim awards have been made on issues that appear to be related to jurisdiction. This has led to questions regarding the manner in which these cases should be handled, either as an award under Section or as an interim award under Section 31(6) of the Act. Another contentious issue that has been brought up in connection with this is the fact that there have been cases in which interim awards have been made on issues that appear to be related to jurisdiction. In the recent case of *M/s Indian Farmers Fertilizer Co. vs. M/s Bhadra Products*¹⁵, the Supreme Court of India made the decision that an award on the question of limitation is to be viewed as an interim award and may be appealed in accordance with Section 34¹⁶ of the Arbitration Act. In the case of *NTPC vs. Siemens*¹⁷, the court struggled with the question of the statute of limitations, and now it has reached a conclusion. The Supreme Court arrived at the judgement that an award is regarded to be binding on the parties as an interim award if it finally ends a disagreement that existed between them.¹⁸ In addition, the problem of limitation was differentiated from a jurisdictional issue by the fact that issues of jurisdiction are the ones that are specifically stipulated in Section 16 of the Act. This includes questions regarding the validity of an arbitration agreement, the constitution of the arbitral tribunal, and whether or not the subject matter of the dispute is covered under the arbitration clause. In addition, this includes questions regarding whether or not the dispute is covered under the arbitration clause. As a direct consequence of this, the process that is described in Section 16 of the document could not be carried out in this specific instance of the case. The court ruled in the case *Noida Toll Bridge Co. Ltd. vs. Mitsui Marubeni Corporation*¹⁹ that a decision of an arbitral tribunal that is not concerned with the competence of the tribunal but instead deals with a legal infirmity attributed to the claim in itself is an interim award and cannot be taken as a decision on the jurisdiction of the case. This ruling was made in light of the fact that the arbitral tribunal was not concerned with the competence of the tribunal. This decision was reached in light of the fact that the arbitral tribunal was not compelled to consider the issue of the arbitral tribunal’s own competence in making decisions. As a consequence of this, the decision of the arbitral tribunal that an unregistered partnership firm has the right to make claims before it and that the statutory bar outlined in Section 69 of the Partnership Act, 1932 is inapplicable was deemed to be an interim award rather than a decision on the jurisdiction of the tribunal. This was the result of the

¹⁴ Deepak Mitra v. D.J. Alld., AIR 2000 All 9.

¹⁵ M/s Indian Farmers Fertilizer Co. v. M/s Bhadra Products, 2018 SCC Online SC 38, ¶16, 29.

¹⁶ Arbitration & Conciliation Act 1996 § 34.

¹⁷ National thermal Power Corporation Ltd. v. Siemens Atkiengesellschaft, (2007) 1 Arb LR 377.

¹⁸ Naval Sharma, Shriya Luke, India: *Interim Award on Limitation Can Be Challenged Under Section 34 of the Arbitration & Conciliation Act 1996*, MONDAQ

<http://www.mondaq.com/india/x/667478/trials+appeals+compensation/Interim+award+on+limitation+can+be+challenged+under+Section+34+of+the+Arbitration+Conciliation+Act+1996>.

¹⁹ Noida Toll Bridge Co. Ltd. v. Mitsui Marubeni Corporation, (2005) 3 Arb LR 234.

holding that the decision of the arbitral tribunal was an interim award. This came about as a result of the conclusion that the legislative restriction outlined in Section 69 of the Partnership Act of 1932 does not apply in the given circumstances.²⁰

What is the key distinction between an ‘interim award’ and a ‘interim measure’?

An interim measure must be differentiated from an interim award by analysing the aim of the order and the degree to which it is definite concerning the rights and duties of the parties. It is essential to emphasise this distinction, as it is vital to bring attention to it. An interim order is a form of temporary measure of relief that may be granted in order to safeguard certain rights that are held by the parties involved in a legal dispute.²¹ This kind of relief may be issued in order to prevent the situation from deteriorating further. It is impossible to consider an interim award that was made apparently under Section 17 to be an order of interim relief because it was not made with the intention of providing protection for the subject matter.²² An order of interim relief must be made with the intention of providing protection for the subject matter. In spite of the fact that the arbitrator has said that the award is being made in accordance with Section 17 and has also granted security, the fact that the award is one that is regarded to be an interim award in accordance with Section 31(6) has not been altered by these facts.²³ It has been decided that a mandatory award that directs payment of certain sums by one party to the other based on a prima facie determination on the list, but that is not in the nature of a final determination of the rights of the party, is an interim award and that it falls within the ambit of Section 31(6).²⁴ This decision was made based on the reasoning that the award is not in the nature of a final determination of the rights of the party. The rationale for this judgement was that the award did not have the characteristics of a conclusive finding of the party’s rights. Based on this logic, the decision was rendered. An interim arrangement is different from both an interim award and an interim measure in the sense that it is intended to stay in place throughout the duration of the proceedings themselves. This distinguishes an intermediate arrangement from both of those other types of interim measures and awards. On the other hand, any arrangement of this sort that was allowed for in arbitration procedures was considered to have terminated once the processes came to a close. This was because it was presumed that the proceedings had reached their conclusion.²⁵

Because of this, it is reasonable to conclude from the previous explanation that the terms of reference, the conclusiveness of substantive rights, and the closeness of the problem with the contract will each have an impact on the question of defining the character of a judgement as an interim award. This is because the terms of reference, conclusiveness of substantive rights, and closeness of the problem with the contract are all interrelated. As a result of the decision that was handed down in the case of Bhadra Products²⁶, the

²⁰ *Id.*

²¹ Adya Pandey, *Tracing the Steps of Emergency Arbitration in India*, THE WORLD JOURNAL ON JURISTIC POLITY, 1, 5(2017).

²² I A. WADHWA & A. KRISHNAN, JUSTICE RS BACHAWAT’S LAW OF ARBITRATION 1686 (6 ed. Lexis Nexis 2018).

²³ *Asian Electronics Ltd. v. M.P. State Electricity Board*, (2007) 3 MPLJ 203 (DB).

²⁴ *Supra* note 23.

²⁵ *Nand Singh v. Hazoor Singh*, (1996) Supp Arb LR 453 (Del).

²⁶ *M/s Indian Farmers Fertilizer Co. v. M/s Bhadra Products*, 2018 SCC Online SC 38, ¶20-28.

line between jurisdictional awards and interim awards is now much more apparent. In spite of the progress that has been made, it has become clear that the precedential rules that have been formed are very subjective and may be swayed in any direction. This is the case despite the fact that there have been good developments. When dealing with the difficult issues of orders, awards, and jurisdiction, a large degree of faith must be placed in the wisdom of the tribunal and the court in order to find a solution.

JUDICIAL PROCESSING OF INTERIM ARBITRAL AWARDS, WITH A PARTICULAR EMPHASIS ON DISCRETION, CLAIMS FOR REIMBURSEMENT, AND THE POTENTIAL TO BE ENFORCED.

Will the tribunal decide how much is too much in this case?

Regarding the extent and level of judicial intrusion, the Courts have usually acknowledged the arbitral tribunal's discretion in the granting of an interim award. This is because the arbitral tribunal has more experience and expertise in the subject matter. The Bombay High Court has decided that it is both 'reasonable' and 'moderate,' as well as in the best interest of both parties, to order the consortium of lenders to wait for the arbitrators to pass the interim award before claiming their money.²⁷ This decision was reached in light of the fact that the court found it to be in the best interest of both parties. The Court went on to clarify that if the interim award did not go in favour of the debtor, the lenders would be free to immediately take steps to enforce the pledged security of 20 lakhs shares of the company without having to further refer the matter to the Court.²⁸ The Court stated that this would be the case even if the debtor appealed the decision of the interim award. It is a generally accepted principle, both as a matter of authority and as a matter of principle, that the arbitral tribunal has complete discretion over the decision of whether or not to issue an interim award.²⁹ This principle was established both as a matter of authority and as a matter of principle. Because there was no point of law created by the way in which the majority arbitrators used their discretion and there was no basis on which the exercise of their discretion could be questioned, a notice of motion in an arbitral appeal was rejected as a result.³⁰

It is possible to observe that in the absence of any agreement to the contrary, the arbitrators have considerable discretion in the grant and subject matter of the interim award. This discretion can, consequently, cause less uniformity and certainty, lowering the attractiveness of India as a seat of arbitration. In order to combat this, the courts have mandated that the arbitral tribunal is required to make the award only after a proper hearing. This is with the exception of exceptional cases in which the arbitrators can properly find that they are not satisfied that the defence or set-off is made in good faith, or in which there is a sum that is properly due on the basis of the respondent's own

²⁷ Kalyan Sangam Infratech Ltd v IDBI Bank Ltd, 2015 SCC Online Bom 2055.

²⁸ Lenders can claim dues only after passing of Interim Award,

<https://www.sconline.com/blog/post/2015/05/06/lenders-can-claim-dues-only-after-passing-of-interim-award/>

²⁹ 1 A. WADHWA & A. KRISHNAN, JUSTICE RS BACHAWAT'S LAW OF ARBITRATION 1689 (6 ed. Lexis Nexis 2018).

³⁰ Ex mar BV v. National Iranian Tanker Co., (1992) 1 LLOYD'S REP 169.

figures.³¹ Guidelines of the aforementioned sort, which do not amount to orders, could offer a valuable guide for regulating the behaviour of the tribunal and avoiding the difficulties that accompany ever-fluctuating discretion.

The Interplay Between Enforcement and Stay: -

In accordance with Section 36 of the Act and the requirements of the Code of Civil Procedure, 1908 (the 'Code'), an interim award may be enforced as a decree of the court in line with the provisions of the Act. In the context of a final arbitral award, there is no automatic stay on the operation of the award, even if there is an application to set aside the decision under Section 34 pending with the Court. This is because there is no automatic stay on the operation of the award. In spite of this, it is essential to bear in mind the decision of the court on the interim awards.

In the case of *V. Raghavan v. Dr. R. Venkitapathy*³², the Madras High Court made the observation that what is contemplated under Section 36 of the said Act is only the postponement of the enforcement of the award and not the stay of further proceedings by the Arbitral Tribunal pursuant to an interim award. This statement was made in the context of the Madras High Court's decision in *V. Raghavan vs. Dr. R. Venkitapathy*. Therefore, it would seem that the Arbitral Tribunal's ability to issue the ultimate decision cannot be halted by the ongoing procedures before the Court under Section 34, which challenge the interim verdict. In spite of this, the situation is still unclear since there is not a single precedent that can be used to establish a clear viewpoint.

The opportune moment to challenge, with a response to those who advocate for a "piecemeal challenge": -

In spite of the pro-arbitration climate that is prevalent in the judicial sensibilities, the future discourse in this regard may be altered in light of the observations made by the Supreme Court in the *Bhadra Products*³³ case. In that case, Justice Nariman expressed his opinion that the Parliament should make a provision so that all interim awards may be consolidated with the final award, and that a combined challenge to both of these awards may be filed under Section 34 of the Act. This would avoid the trend of a piecemeal if this recommendation is accepted, it will effectively take away the right of the party that is suffering to approach the Court on substantive issues until the final award has been rendered. By that point, the parties may have suffered damage that cannot be repaired as a result of the execution of the interim award. Additionally, in such a circumstance, the arbitration processes would continue based on the basis of the determined interim award, without addressing the opposing views in court, which would eventually minimise the scope of hearings on subsequent matters relating to the dispute. An interim award that held that the contract was validly terminated would greatly reduce the scope of the damages hearing in a hypothetical situation involving an arbitration arising from a construction contract. In this scenario, a contractor claims damages for wrongful termination of the contract and payment for work done, while

³¹ 1 A. WADHWA & A. KRISHNAN, JUSTICE RS BACHAWAT'S LAW OF ARBITRATION 1688 (6 ed. Lexis Nexis 2018).

³² *V. Raghavan v. Dr. R. Venkitapathy*, 2015 SCC Online Mad 8514.

³³ *M/s Indian Farmers Fertilizer Co. v. M/s Bhadra Products*, 2018 SCC Online SC 38, ¶29.

the employer counter-claims for costs incurred in engaging a replacement contractor.³⁴ In view of these significant drawbacks, the counter-argument presented by the Supreme Court, which focuses on reducing costs and avoiding needless delay, would not be able to sufficiently protect the interests of the parties involved. As a result, it is necessary to strike a balance in order to address the potential downsides that were brought up by the Court.

PRELIMINARY ARBITRATION REGARDING LEGAL LIABILITY AND POSSIBLE CONTRACT CONCLUSION.

The criteria that must be adhered to when delivering a judgement on admissions are quite similar to those that must be adhered to when giving an interim award on admissions. This is because Order XII Rule 6 of the Code³⁵ stipulates that the criteria that must be adhered to in both situations are virtually identical. The court determined in the instance of *Numero Uno*³⁶ that an arbitrator may still issue an interim award in the initial action or claim if it can be demonstrated that such an award is otherwise justifiable. This decision was made by the court after considering the evidence presented in the case. This included, among other things, interim awards that had been issued based on culpability that the parties had previously acknowledged to. The court agreed with this judgement and affirmed it. The fact that the defendant has also filed a counterclaim is the one and only condition that would make interference lawful in this situation. Another situation would be the presence of some areas of dispute that have not yet been determined but are unconnected to the subject matter of the interim award. This would be considered a separate circumstance.³⁷ The court went on to decide that in the event that the counterclaim is successful, adjustments to the final award could be made after taking into account the sum that was previously provided in the interim judgement. This ruling came as a result of the court's earlier decision.³⁸

Contracting based on an initial award made as an interim award: -

It would seem that the authority to issue an interim award that is granted by Section 31(6) of the Act and the authority to make such an award that is granted by Section 27 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1940 (commonly known as “the 1940 Act”) are very comparable to one another. The other difference is that section 27 of the 1940 Act started with the words “*unless a different purpose emerges in the arbitration agreement...*”. The only other distinction is that section 27³⁹ of the 1940 Act did not begin with those words. It is important to note that the omission of these terms does not mean that the parties have lost their right to agree to a single award that will be delivered encompassing all concerns. This interpretation runs counter to what the clause was trying to accomplish in the first place. Given that the Act's Section 19(2) states that the

³⁴ *Supra* note 6.

³⁵ *Numero Uno International Ltd. v Prasar Bharti*, 2008(1) ArbLR 446(Delhi) ¶1.

³⁶ *Numero Uno International Ltd. v Prasar Bharti*, 2008(1) ArbLR 446(Delhi) ¶7.

³⁷ Yaman Kumar, Gunjan Chhabra, Award On Admitted Liability In Arbitration Proceedings, <http://www.mondaq.com/india/x/485728/Arbitration+Dispute+Resolution/Interim+Award+On+Admitted+Liability+In+Arbitration+Proceedings>.

³⁸ *Supra* note 35.

³⁹ Arbitration Act 1940 § 27.

parties are free to agree on the procedure that will be followed by the arbitral tribunal in conducting proceedings, it would appear that it would be possible for the parties to choose to rule out an interim award by agreement. This is because the Act states that the parties are free to agree on the procedure that will be followed by the arbitral tribunal in conducting proceedings. This would be conceivable owing to the fact that Section 19(2) of the Act specifies that the parties are free to agree on the method that would be followed by the arbitral tribunal. In other words, the arbitral tribunal would have to follow whatever procedure the parties agree upon.⁴⁰

In spite of the fact that the aforementioned premise is correct, an interim award cannot go against the restrictions that are outlined in the contract.⁴¹ An interim award that directed the owner to execute the sale deed even when the apartments were not complete was held to be without jurisdiction. This is because, according to the contract, owners were only obligated to execute the sale deed after the owner's share of apartments were completed in all respects. The award that directed the owner to do so even when the apartments were not complete was held to be without jurisdiction. The court decided that the award in question did not have the authority to issue a ruling since it instructed the property owner to sign the sale deed even while the units remained unfinished.⁴² Therefore, despite the fact that it is possible to exclude Section 31(6), that is, to impose a complete or partial restriction on the grant of interim awards by virtue of an agreement to the contrary, an arbitrator or court will not be permitted to go beyond the contract in the event that the parties have not made such an agreement to the contrary. This is because Section 31(6) makes it possible to exclude Section 31(6), which means that it is possible to impose a complete or partial restriction on the grant of interim awards. This is owing to the fact that although while it is possible to omit Section 31(6), also known as imposing a full or partial limitation on the awarding of interim awards by virtue of an agreement to the contrary, it is not required to do so in order to comply with the regulations.

CONCLUSION

We have noticed that important issues are still left to be decided and applied at the whim of the tribunal and the Court on a case-by-case basis, despite the fact that the Courts have established some guidelines for how to deal with interim awards. This is despite the fact that the Courts have established some guidelines for how to deal with interim awards. In spite of the fact that the Courts have set certain guidelines, this remains the situation. The recommendation that was given as leaving comments in the Bhadra Products case is excessive in the sense that it would rob the parties of their capacity to seek recourse during the interim stage, and it does not seem to be the appropriate choice. The proposition was presented as a parting comment. When it comes to dealing with challenges to interim awards, the parties do wind up spending a substantial amount of time and money, which is why the concern that the Court has in

⁴⁰ 1 A. WADHWA & A. KRISHNAN, JUSTICE RS BACHAWAT'S LAW OF ARBITRATION 1682 (6 ed. Lexis Nexis 2018).

⁴¹ *Id.*

⁴² V.N. Krishna Rao v. Turnkey Constructions Pvt. Ltd., AIR 2004 NOC 350 (Kant).

issuing such a recommendation is a reasonable one. These challenges also pose a threat to the efficacy of the newly introduced Section 29A, which imposes a time limit of one year to complete arbitration proceedings and grant the final award, with the possibility of only a one-time extension of six months if the parties mutually consent to the extension. If the parties do not mutually consent to the extension, then the time limit will remain at one year. On the other hand, this issue may be resolved if both the tribunal and the court adopt a consistent discretionary approach. The suggestion of the court to make such a change is also included in this statement. As was said before, it may be useful if the Supreme Court lays down specific norms for tribunal and lower courts as and when such a case comes before it for adjudication. This would be the first time such a matter would be brought before the Supreme Court. When the case is argued before the Supreme Court, this would be the point at which it would be decided. If the terms of the contract imply that it would be beneficial to render a single award, then the parties should be strongly encouraged to expressly opt out of Section 31(6) and expressly bar the grant of interim awards if any arbitration proceedings ensue. This would be the best course of action in this situation. This will avoid additional expenditures and delays from developing that are not essential. It is possible that Section 36 of the Act may be amended so that it contains provisions for the execution of interim awards and stops arbitration processes while such awards are being enforced. If this occurs, the revision would be considered a change to the Act. As a result of this, Section 29A, which, as was stated earlier, mandates that the final award must be issued within a time limit of one year, may also be amended to stipulate concessions in which an interim award is granted, with the intention of preventing the dissolution of the tribunal upon the occurrence of the prescribed time period's expiration. This would be done with the goal of preserving the integrity of the legal system. It would be beneficial to permit an expedited hearing to the challenge to the interim award in order to limit the amount of time that is wasted waiting for the hearing; it may be beneficial to alter Section 34 of the Act to this extent. This would be helpful in minimising the amount of time that is wasted. It is necessary that the precedents be adhered to in a rigorous way in order to guarantee that there is no interference with the finality of the interim ruling. This may be ensured by ensuring that there is no deviation from the precedents. Although the amendments would increase the degree of certainty, judicial certainty will not prevail until the tribunal and the Courts conform to precedents, adopt a pro-arbitration approach, and *suo moto* deploy all possible methods to reduce costs and delays. Until this happens, judicial certainty will not prevail. Judicial certainty can only be attained via the use of this one approach.